

THE IMPORTANCE OF CARTOONS FOR INCREASING PUPILS' VOCABULARY (PADDINGTON)

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Abstract. *Vocabulary is considered as a significant factor in language learning. Without enough knowledge of words and their meaning, learners are not able to use them correctly and effectively. Moreover, vocabulary can be forgotten easily, if it is not provided some examples or explanations from daily life. Aborting idioms is among difficult areas of learning a second language since most of idioms are not exist their mother tongue. Most teachers address media such as videos, pictures, animations and interactive games, CDs or DVDs, the use of the internet, chat rooms and video conferencing in order to make lessons enjoyable, understandable as well as productive. In addition, nowadays using movies in the lessons is being chosen by variety of teachers for increasing students` real life communication vocabularies. While watching movies especially primary school children not only be aware of use of words, but also get entrainment, even can learn American culture.*

Keywords: *movies, subtitles, vocabulary, idioms.*

INTRODUCTION

There are many crucial linguistic features like grammar, pronunciation and of course vocabulary. Vocabulary is significant factor for success, without knowing idioms`, phrasal verbs` meaning, students may misunderstand. As non-native speakers of English language, it is sometimes difficult to know where and how sounds are formed in the mouth. They may not naturally be able to handle English phonology since a specific sound that a learner cannot produce does not exist in their native language. [1]. As most language learners aim to develop successful communication and literacy skills, they have to first learn enough words and to know how to use these words appropriately as very little can be said with grammar, but almost anything can be said with words [2]. Till the late '80s and early '90s, language was taught by using only huge books and dictionaries, and the process was not effective at all, since new vocabulary learned through textbooks tends to be forgotten. The main reason why students could not deal with challenging vocabularies was boredom. However, by the mid '90s many multimedia language programs like videos, pictures, animations and interactive games, CDs or DVDs, movies, became popular on the internet and they affect development of learning and teaching methodologies that making the students enjoy and create productively. Besides, as nowadays methodology changes day by day, attracting foreign specialists in the sphere of pedagogy seems to be a right decision [3]. Most students prefer movies to traditional printed textbooks which they can see only dead words and sentences. Films are motivating for EFL/ESL teaching because they embody the notion that a film with a story that wants to be told rather than a lesson that needs to be taught [4].

Learners would become more excited to use this new way of teaching and learning. They would be more eager to understand the new vocabularies and remember them for a longtime. Learning with the help of movies will give a chance to get acquainted with the native voice and as

a result their listening skills can be improved. Ismaili's (2013) [5] study analyzed the effects of using movies in the EFL classroom and it revealed its effects on developing students listening and communication skill. When students watch movies, they focus on process, characters of the movie, so they will feel free from pressure and stressful situation in traditional language classes. Consequently, they learn the language incidentally. Film communication offers links between classrooms and society. Films can help explore cultural context, maybe integrated easily into the curriculum, are entertaining. And allow flexibility of materials and teaching techniques, [6]. The use of idioms is so widespread that their understanding is essential to successful communication [7]. The data from Experiments 2 and 3 indicate that people view idioms as having more complex meanings than do their roughly, equivalent literal paraphrases [8]. A considerable body of research affirms that a strong knowledge of idioms will help language learners to be better speakers and negotiators and they will be in a better position to use their knowledge in appropriate contexts [9].

METHODOLOGY

Movie Paddington [10] was released in 2015 by Studio Canal, Anton production. The movies' genres are comedy and family. It is about a young Peruvian bear travels to London in search of a home. Finding himself lost and alone at Paddington Station, he meets the kindly Brown family, who offer him a temporary haven. The Brown family is very kind and friendly. Even Paddington is a bear, they accept him as a family member. This movie teaches variety of parents how to be good parents as Mr. Brown and Mrs. Brown.

RESULTS

There are explanations and examples of some idioms that used in Paddington movie.

1. Stow away.

What it means: To hide on a ship, aircraft, or other vehicle in order to escape from a place or to travel without paying.

How it is used:

In 14:12, When Paddington describes his trip.

Jonathan: How did you get here?

Paddington: I stowed away. In a lifeboat.

Examples from real life:

*Once he'd got the cord **stowed away** tidily in a big paper bag, he peered out the window, looking left and right, as he'd been doing for the previous quarter of an hour.*

*And even if she got to the coast on her own, she might **stow away** on the wrong ship.*

*"Perhaps he **stowed away** on a ship," she mumbled.*

2. Bunk up.

What it means: To share a room, bed, or other sleeping space with another person.

How it is used:

In 22:51, When Jonathan is having a conversation with his sister.

Jonathan: Where is he going to sleep?

Jody: Not in my room. He is he.

Jonathan: Tony is a he and he would be more welcome to a bunk-up.

Examples from real life:

*You will need to **bunk up** with your sister because we weren't able to reserve enough hotel rooms for everyone.*

*We became best friends after we **bunked up** at camp.*

Although Sam only has a single bed, he needs to **bunk up** with brother every night.

3. Take charge (of something).

What it means: To accept responsibility for something and have control over it.

How it is used:

In 41:51, When Mr. Brown is making a decision about Paddington.

Mr. Brown: I am taking charge! Paddington is a danger to this family.

Examples from real life:

*She **took charge of the project** and made sure it was finished on time.*

*It was a great relief when Heather arrived and **took charge of the project**.*

*A neighbor **took charge of the children** until he got home from the emergency room.*

4. Be more to this than meets the eye.

What it means: If there is more to something than meets the eye, it is more difficult to understand or involves more things than you thought at the beginning.

How it is used:

In 42:39, When Mrs. Bird is describing Mr. Brown.

Jonathan: Dad has always been boring and annoying.

Mrs. Bird: Oh, I don't know about that. More to your father than meets the eye.

Examples from real life:

*This whole business is very puzzling. There is a lot more to it **than meets the eye**.*

*There is more to this proposal **than meets the eye**.*

*There's more to this apparently ordinary table **than meets the eye**.*

5. Be crawling with something.

What it means: To be completely covered with or full of a particular type of thing.

How it is used:

In 54:10, When explorer's daughter is having a talk with Mr. Curry.

Explorer's daughter: It always starts with just one. Soon, the whole street will be crawling with them.

Examples from real life:

*After the bomb scare, the airport **was crawling with police**.*

*The bread **they gave us was crawling with ants** and completely inedible.*

*It was obvious to us that the hotel **was crawling with spies**.*

6. Get cracking.

What it means: To start doing something quickly.

How it is used:

In 57:31, When the Browns are leaving home.

Mr. Brown: Let's get cracking.

Mrs. Brown: Oh, wait, please.

Examples from real life:

***Get cracking**, or we'll miss the train.*

*I'd better **get cracking** on the food for tonight.*

*Mark, you'd better **get cracking**, the sooner the better.*

7. The last straw.

What it means: The last in a series of unpleasant events that finally makes you feel that you cannot continue to accept a bad situation.

How it is used:

In 1:02:18, Used by Mr. Brown, when he was arguing.

Mr. Brown: I am sorry, but that was the last straw.

Mrs. Brown: It was an accident. They happen.

Examples from real life:

*Losing my job was bad enough, but being evicted was **the final straw**.*

*She's always been rude to me, but it **was the last straw** when she started insulting my mother.*

***The last straw was** when the company fired most of the managers.*

CONCLUSION

Learning new vocabulary and their meaning, as a demanding task of most second language learners plays an essential part in language learning, especially in increasing their communication skills. The increasing access to different multimedia, including subtitled movies offers students variety numbers of opportunities to improve their vocabulary. The role of subtitles in helping learners` through the process of vocabulary acquisition has been seen by a lot of scholars. Thus, a great deal of research has been conducted on exploring the effectiveness of watching subtitled movies in vocabulary acquisition. Previous studies have found out several benefits of using subtitled movies by confirming that subtitles indeed improve vocabulary learning.

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